

Resolving unexpected bacterial species alignments

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Abstract

Phylogenies regularly show unexpected discrepancies. These can arise for a number of reasons, but errors in identification or sequencing are arguably a better place to determine why there is a discrepancy than assuming heterogenous gene copies involving horizontal gene transfer or other causes.

Recognising an anomaly exists is easily missed where a review does not align a wide enough range of species. Thus a species misplaced to family is readily dismissed if only one family is being considered. Use of a tool, such as BLAST, will readily identify the anomalous sequence's closest genetic relatives.

A recent review of *Rhizobiaceae* and closely associated families within Hyphomicrobiales to determine a better family placement of *Liberibacter* species, important crop pathogens, revealed two sequences completely out of their expected family and related species clade placements. This analysis looked more closely at them.

The sequence AF035049, identified as *Mesorhizobium huakuii* subsp. *rengei*, did not align with other members of the species or genus, but BLAST aligned it with *Acidivorax* species. Ultimately it appears that an automated system applied one name to two different sequences, both identified as strain B3. The badly aligned sequence was identified during the sequence deposition as an unknown bacterium within the *Betaproteobacteria*. AF035049 simply required the incorrect name and family placement to be removed. LPSN has already done this.

The species *Mycoplana bullata*, almost universally placed within *Rhizobiaceae* or *Bartonellaceae*, did not align well. Using the BLAST tool, the closest genetic relatives were readily identified as belonging to species within *Caulobacteraceae*. Literature search revealed that this species, described in 1928, was originally misidentified and a proposal to change the name had been validly published in 2009. Clearly this change is still required.

Introduction

In an earlier 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis to resolve the family placement of the important crop pathogens *Liberibacter* (Nelson 2026), particularly focusing on the *Hyphomicrobiaceae*, *Rhizobiaceae*, *Bartonellaceae* and adjacent families within

Hyphomicrobiales, it became obvious that two sequences aligned well outside the current family placements.

The two outliers are *Mycoplana bullata* (*Rhizobiaceae*) and *Mesorhizobium huakuii* (*Bartonellaceae*), bolded names at the top of the cladogram (Figure 1). However, without a broader range of families represented in the analysis, this difference could simply be a common difference noted between trees derived from 16S and genomic methods (Naranjo-Robayo et al. 2026) and thus simply aligning poorly within Hyphomicrobiales

The objective was to determine why these species were so completely removed from other representatives of their families.

Figure 1: Cladogram showing alignment of Hyphomicrobiales 16S rRNA genes. Collapsed clades are family or genus clades. The Bartonellaceae and Rhizobiaceae species at the top of the cladogram in bold, while clearly out of place, do not suggest they are significantly misclassified.

Methods

16S rRNA gene sequences were obtained from the List of Prokaryotic names with Standing in Nomenclature ([LPSN](#)) (Freese et al. 2026) for genera within *Aurantimonadaceae*, *Bartonellaceae*, *Devosiaceae*, *Hyphomicrobiaceae*, *Kaisteaceae*, *Methyloligollaceae*, *Nitrobacteraceae* and *Rhizobiaceae*. These were aligned using ClustalX (Larkin et al. 2007) using the faster UPGM algorithm for ribosomal genes (Larkin et al. 2007) and the resultant guideline visualised in the Interactive Tree of Life ([ITOL](#)) (Letunic & Bork 2024).

The [BLAST](#) tool (Altschul et al. 1990) was used to find the closest match for the species in question, selecting the rRNA database and highly similar sequences options (megablast), but otherwise default parameters. BLAST accessed May 2026. Genomes were also obtained for these species from the [NCBI](#) database (Sayers et al. 2025), with multiple copies of 16S rRNA gene sequences downloaded and compared for heterogeneity.

Alignments were visually inspected for major discrepancies and likely sequence errors (often nucleotide positions marked as N). In many cases, this was best conducted by aligning smaller collections of sequences. Sequences with major sections well beyond the 5' or 3' ends had these manually truncated. Isolated sequences with major apparent insertions, in excess of 10 nucleotides, were removed for this analysis on the assumption of a likely error in the sequence. Sequences less than 1350 nt length were also discarded.

Results and Discussion

Initial overview

Family placement of the large number of species showed two outliers, namely one *Mesorhizobium* (*Bartonellaceae*) and one *Mycoplana* (*Rhizobiaceae*) sequence as complete outliers (Figure 1).

Inspection of the aligned sequences showed obvious visible differences between these two species with the rest of the species sequences. Were these species subject to heterogeneity in 16S genes, sequencing errors or misidentifications?

The type strain genomes of *Mesorhizobium huakii* (CP139858) and *Mycoplana bullata* (CP139996 but named *Brevundimonas bullata* in GenBank) contain two and three identical copies of the 16S rRNA gene respectively. This clarified that the misplacements were not an artifact of horizontal gene transfer or other significant heterogeneity for either species.

BLAST analysis of each of these species suggested a close relationship with *Acidivorax* species and *Brevundimonas* species respectively. Adding species from these genera to the initial aligned range confirmed their close positioning within these genera (Figure 2). This suggests these errors represent a *Mesorhizobium* (Alphaproteobacteria) species actually belonging in Betaproteobacteria, and a *Mycoplana* (*Hyphomicrobiales*) species belonging in *Brevundimonas* (*Caulobacterales*).

Figure 2: *Mesorhizobium* and *Mycoplana* (bolded species) showing their fit amongst the *Brevundimonas* and *Acidivorax* clades respectively. Cladogram using 16S rRNA gene sequences.

Mesorhizobium huakuii subsp *regei* B3 AF035049

Surprisingly, BLAST responses indicated this sequence (AF035049) was most closely related to members of the *Comamonadaceae* and specifically *Acidovorax* species (Figure 3). These are members of the Betaproteobacteria, a different Class to the Alphaproteobacteria where the rest of the genera and species in this figure are based. It does appear to be a bit

of an outlier in the family *Comamonadaceae*, but still appears to be solidly within the broader apparently monophyletic clade of this family. Resolution of this placement is beyond the scope of this analysis. This family is a member of the *Burkholderiales*, an order including a number of important medical and environmental importance. However, they are very readily separated using 16S gene analysis from members of the *Alphaproteobacteria*.

Comamonadaceae are commonly associated with root nodules (Rivera-Hernandez et al 2024) and some may also fix nitrogen (Willems et al 1991).

Figure 3: The sequence AF035049 has been identified as *M. huakuii* subsp. *reingei*, strain B3 (bolded). It aligns closely with the *Acidovorax/Comamonas* species complex. AB0150965 is a very short (300bp) sequence identified as *M. huakuii* subsp. *reingei* aligning with the other *Mesorhizobium* species.

Taxonomic history

First published as *Rhizobium huakuii* (Chen et al 1991) derived from nitrogen-fixing root nodules on the legume *Astragalus sinicus* L. It was placed in *Rhizobium* by comparison with other species in this genus, as well as those from *Bradyrhizobium*, *Agrobacterium* and *Sinorhizobium*, all members of the *Rhizobiaceae*, based on numerical taxonomy, phenotypic features, GC% content comparisons and DNA hybridisation. This species, along with a few other species, were separated into a new genus, *Mesorhizobium* (Jarvis et al 1997), based on similarity of these species to *R. loti*, the type species of this new genus. The taxonomic tools at the time indicated strong commonalities amongst these *Mesorhizobium* species. This analysis shows no issues with placement of this species alongside other *Mesorhizobium* species.

M. huakuii subsp. *reingei*, described from *Astragalus sinicus* grown in Japan, with strain B3 as the type (Nuswantara et al 1999), was separated from the species based on the short 300bp 16S sequence (AB015965.1) and other taxonomic features. It is not regarded as validly published (LPSN). This 300bp fragment results in other *Mesorhizobium* species as the closest match by BLAST.

The near full length 16S sequence (AF035049) is clearly not a *Mesorhizobium* species (Figure 3). The GenBank entry indicates it is a Betaproteobacterium strain B3 but otherwise unnamed and connected with other *Comamonadaceae* species descriptions (Kalmbach et al

1999). This error in LPSN likely arises since *M. huakuii* subsp. *rengei* B3 (AB015965) and the unnamed Betaproteobacterium (AF035049) are both identified as strains B3.

Suggested taxonomic revision

Further taxonomic assessment for the sequence [AF035049](#) is required but beyond the scope of this analysis, although it clearly aligns within or close to Betaproteobacteria in the *Acidovorax/Comamonas/Melaminivora* species complex in *Comamonadaceae*. It thus remains as an unnamed bacterium, described in GenBank as “Beta proteobacterium B3 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence”. It needs to be removed from *Mesorhizobium* records.

LPSN have been notified that the 16S sequence is incorrectly named. The sequence AF035049 now no longer appears in this database under *Mesorhizobium*.

No change is suggested for *M. huakii* subsp. *rengei* (Genbank AB015965), as it aligns correctly with *M. huakuii* D13431 (Figure 3). Whether this subspecies itself is taxonomically sound is beyond the scope of this investigation.

Mycoplana bullata

This species appeared out of place in the earlier study of *Liberibacter* species (Nelson 2026) (Figure 1). BLAST analysis of sequence D12785 indicated this species is much better aligned with *Brevundimonas* species (Figure 2). The existence of sequences of *Brevundimonas bullata* (sequences NR_025831.1 and NR_113611.1) as the closest match, as well as many other *Brevundimonas* species as close matches too, indicates why the sequence D12785 aligned well away from other *Rhizobiaceae* (Figure 1). More peculiar is that sequence NR_025831.1 is noted to be strain IAM 13153, the same strain identification as *Mycoplana bullata* sequence D12785, thus the same strain (IAM 13153) has been deposited under both genera.

Taxonomic history

Mycoplana, type species *Mycoplana dimorpha*, is a genus described as “fungus wanderer” and was first defined in 1928 (Gray & Thornton 1928 cited by, Urakami et al. 1990) as a group of soil bacteria with branching cells. Prior to genetic sequencing material, morphological characteristics and subsequent taxonomic studies placed the genus in *Mycobacteraceae* or *Pseudomonadaceae*, Alphaproteobacteria and Gammaproteobacteria respectively, and later *Brucellaceae*, but revised in the type species analysis to *Rhizobiaceae* (Hördt et al. 2020). Placement of *Mycoplana* species in or near *Rhizobiaceae* is confirmed here (Figure 4), except for *M. bullata* which strongly aligns better within *Caulobacteriaceae*.

Figure 4: Cladogram showing position of the current four *Mycoplana* species with 16S sequences in LPSN, with *M. bullata* clearly aligning well within the *Brevundimonas* genus of *Caulobacteraceae*,

M. dimorpha, and *M. bullata* were confirmed as species, separate from but close to *Methylobacterium* and *Xanthobacter* based on structural and chemosystematic data (Urakami et al. 1990). In a review of *Rhizobiaceae*, *M. bullata*, locating close to *Pseudomonas* (now *Brevundimonas*) *diminuta*, was recommended to be placed in a separate genus from other *Mycoplana* species, but without suggesting a genus (Yanagi & Yamasato 1993), referencing strain IAM 13153 (Genbank D12785). A review of *Caulobacter* and close relatives, noted that *M. bullata* belonged in the genus *Brevundimonas* (Abraham et al. 1999) but suggested further investigation. A review specifically testing 16S rRNA gene sequence phylogenies of rhizobia demonstrated *B. bullata* (citing Abraham et al 1999) falling well

outside the *Rhizobiaceae* genera, including when aligning *atpD* and *recA* gene sequences (Gaunt et al. 2001). (Yoon et al. 2008) noted [*Mycoplana*] *bullata* ATCC 4278T (AJ294364) used as an outgroup comparing species of *Brucella*, *Ochrobactrum*, *Pseudochrobactrum* and *Mycoplana*. Thus the indication that *M. bullata* is misidentified suggests a long overdue identity correction derived from many independent sources.

Description of a novel *Brevundimonas* soil bacterium (Kang et al. 2009) included reclassification of *M. bullata* into this genus as a result of noting the new species was phylogenetically and phenotypically closely related to *Brevundimonas* species, exhibiting 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity of 96.6%-98.0% to other species of *Brevundimonas*. This evolutionary closeness is confirmed in this analysis (Figure 4). Note that the second sequence (NZ_CP139996.1), called *B. bullata*, was sequenced independently as part of a genome collection (Hogle et al. 2024) and from the type strain HAMBI_0262.

The name revision of (Kang et al. 2009) has been used in a number of papers. A novel *Brevundimonas* species was compared by 16S rRNA gene sequence with other members of *Brevundimonas*, including *B. bullata* (TK0051^T sequence D12785) (Chaudhary & Kim 2018). The isolate MB756 aligned with *B. bullata* (D12786), strain IAM 13153 with 99.93% sequence identity, in addition to commonality of G+C% and phenotypic characteristics (Li et al. 2022).

Brevundimonas was erected to hold a few species of *Pseudomonas* based on DNA-rRNA hybridisation and 16S sequencing studies (Segers et al. 1994). Thus they were separated as being members of Alphaproteobacteria, rather than Gammaproteobacteria for *Pseudomonas* species. They are also noted for their prosthecate structure (Tsubouchi et al. 2013). Further, 16S sequencing showed *Brevundimonas* are close to *Caulobacter* and thus now belong in *Caulobacteraceae* (Tsubouchi et al. 2013).

[BacDive](#), accessed May 2026 (Reimer et al. 2022) lists *M. bullata* with synonym *B. bullata* as TK0051 and culture collection numbers DSM 7126, ATCC 4278, ATCC 7980, IAM 13153, JCM 20846, LMG 17157, CCUG 57113, NRRL B-1090, NRRL B-8016, BCRC 11578, CGMCC 4.1472, HAMBI 262, IFO 13290, NBRC 13290, VKM Ac-910. Similarly for LPSN, accessed May 2026 (Freese et al. 2026).

The LPSN record for *Brevundimonas bullata* (Göker 2026) includes the note “*Brevundimonas bullata* is the correct name instead if this species is regarded as a separate species (i.e., if its nomenclatural type is not assigned to another species whose name is validly published, legitimate and not rejected and has priority) within a separate genus *Brevundimonas*.”

The other *Mycoplana* species in this analysis cluster in *Rhizobiaceae* and thus appear to be taxonomically secure. Broader revision of genus placement within the family is beyond the scope of this analysis.

Suggested taxonomic revision

Clearly *M. bullata* is better placed as *B. bullata*, as already proposed by (Kang et al. 2009) and used by (Hogle et al. 2024). Further, *B. bullata* (Gray and Thornton 1928) Kang et al. 2009 is already validly published (Kang et al. 2009).

Mycoplana was described from soil bacteria with an unusual branching cell morphology and the ability to decompose aromatic compounds (Urakami et al. 1990). Taxonomy based on morphology and biochemical features are no longer decisive modern taxonomic characteristics, although they do still have a place. The complex taxonomic history indicates the difficulty of placing these species. The advent of genomic information becoming available resulted in the type species (*M. dimorpha*) being placed into *Rhizobiaceae* (Hördt et al. 2020). Since only type species were considered, this review did not include *M. bullata* and the general assumption would be that members of the same genus belong to the same family. However, misidentification only started being suggested once 16S rRNA gene sequencing was used and demonstrated a misidentification (Yanagi & Yamasato 1993). The formal description of *Brevundimonas bullata* comb. nov. occurred substantially later (Kang et al. 2009).

Regarding the taxonomic note:

- Separate species – there is no question about the species itself. The type is TK0051^T sequence D12785 and applied to both synonyms as noted in both LPSN and BacDive data. It is a question of the more appropriate genus placement. *B. bullata* and *M. bullata* are not separate species but synonyms.
- Nomenclatural type - this does not apply to another species.
- Legitimate and not rejected – both the genus *Brevundimonas* and the species epithet *bullata* are well formed and legitimate names. The name change follows the rules of nomenclature. The species boundary is secure per analysis of (Kang et al. 2009).
- Priority – the name *bullata*, originally as *Mycoplana bullata*, has priority and thus the revision respects this priority.

The description of Kang et al 2009, already used in a number of publications, is clearly an appropriate change. *Mycoplana bullata*, originally misidentified, clearly belongs to the genus *Brevundimonas* and the basonym needs to be changed to *B. bullata*.

Table 1: Summary of taxonomic changes indicated from this analysis

Current name	Relevant sequence	Proposed	Evidence type	Key reference
<i>M. huakuii</i> subsp. <i>rengei</i>	AF035049	Remove incorrect name attached to this sequence from databases	The sequence belongs to an unnamed Betaproteobacteria member, correctly identified as such in GenBank	Genbank entry AF035049, Incorrect name applied in LPSN and subsequently corrected
<i>Mycoplana bullata</i>	D12785	<i>B. bullata</i> as basonym, <i>M. bullata</i> as homotypic synonym	16S sequence alignment, no change in type strain	(Kang et al. 2009) including comb. nov. description

Conclusion

This analysis provides two examples of unusual alignment of two sequences. With relatively few comparative species, especially Family or even Order taxonomic reviews, an unusual alignment will not necessarily alert to substantial misclassification (Table 1).

The first example indicates misclassification across Classes. In this case it appears to be an error arising from a probable automated application of the name of one species to the sequence of another, apparently because they have the same strain epithet of B3. No name change is required, simply removing the incorrectly applied name in databases.

The second example illustrates how long it can take to correct an original misidentification. The original description from 1928, an alert of misclassification in 1993 to a formal and validly published name change in 2009, yet the incorrect name is still commonly used in modern databases. Using the BLAST tool quickly demonstrated where the error lay and then literature searches revealed the required revision documentation.

The fact both *Brevundimonas* and *Rhizobiaceae* species may fix atmospheric nitrogen, often associated with plant roots, potentially influenced the view of *M. bullata* belonging within *Rhizobiaceae*. Use of the term “rhizobacteria” for bacteria isolated from soil and that exhibit nitrogen fixing (Naqqash et al. 2020), regardless of formal taxonomic placement, can easily suggest an explanation for confusing clearly unrelated species and their taxonomic placement. In addition, *Mycoplana* “branching cells” and prosthecate *Brevundimonas* are readily confused visually (Hallgren & Jonas 2025).

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All data used is available from GenBank

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